

CORRELATION OF IMPACT AND DELAMINATION RESISTANCE IN INTERLEAFED LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Interleafing, the incorporation of thin, discrete layers of tough ductile resin at the lamina interfaces, has been shown to significantly improve the impact resistance of graphite/epoxy and graphite/bismaleimide composite material systems. This increase, which is manifested as an increase in residual compression strength after impact, results from the interleaf's ability to alter the pattern of impact damage development. In addition to these results, the effect of interleafing on the material's Mode I and Mode II delamination resistances will also be reviewed in this report. Test results indicate that while only nominal increases in GIC were obtained via interleafing, the material's GIICs were significantly increased. A correlation of these empirical data will be presented.

INTRODUCTION

A unique aspect of composites lies in the fact that the material can be engineered to meet a specific application. Through the choice of resin, fiber, and laminate stacking sequence, the engineer may design a material to fit his structural requirements. As a result of durability and damage tolerance considerations, impact and delamination resistances have become key issues when composite materials are used in structural applications. Indeed, severe reductions in laminate residual tensile and compression strength resulting from low velocity, high mass impact have been reported in the literature [Ref 1-3]. In response to the aircraft industry's demand for improved materials, increased resistance to impact and delamination damage have, likewise, become key issues in designing and developing new composite material systems.

Materials engineers have traditionally addressed this issue through the development of high strain fibers and tougher resins [Ref 4]. An additional variable may be introduced to this formula, however, if a second, separate resin system is added to the composite system. The objective of this approach is to selectively toughen the ply interfaces which delaminate under impact.

This concept, which is known as interleaving [Ref 5], is illustrated schematically in Fig. 1. In this physical construction technique, a thin layer of resin is added to one side of standard prepreg tape (i.e. tape with a 60% fiber volume fraction) which itself contains an improved, tough matrix resin. Advances in resin chemistry are incorporated into the resin used to support the fibers and the vulnerable interlaminar regions are further engineered to improve delamination resistance.

There are two key factors to this approach: first, the interlayer resin used must have a large ultimate shear strain; second, it must remain a discrete layer after the laminate has been cured. Both thermoset and thermoplastic resins have been successfully employed as interleaf systems. Figure 2 contains a photomicrograph of a laminate fabricated using Cyanamid's first generation interleafed product, CYCOM® HST-7, [Ref 5,6]. The thermoset interleaf used in this system co-cures with the matrix. It has sufficient flow control to remain as a discrete layer when the laminate is cured. Materials investigations conducted since the development of CYCOM HST-7 have led to the development of thermoplastic interleaf systems [Ref 7]. Figure 3 contains a photomicrograph of the cross section of a laminate which has been interleafed with one of these thermoplastic films. Such films have been successfully interleafed in both epoxy and bismaleimide composite systems.

This report will detail the results of an investigation of the impact and delamination resistances of interleafed laminates. Experimental results will be presented for several interleafed and noninterleafed graphite/epoxy and graphite/bismaleimide systems. After a brief review of the effectiveness of interleaving in improving damage tolerance, the reasons for the beneficial effect will be explored. The effect of interleaving on the material's Mode I and Mode II delamination resistances will then be discussed. The mechanisms which lead to these results will also be reviewed. Finally, an important result of this investigation is the correlation of delamination resistance with improved impact resistance. A discussion of the correlation of empirical data developed in this study will be presented.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Thermoplastic films were interleafed with several unidirectional graphite/epoxy and graphite/bismaleimide prepreg tape systems in this investigation. The epoxy prepregs studied included CYCOM® 1808 and CYCOM® 1827; the bismaleimide prepregs examined were CYCOM® 3100 and CYCOM® 3100-21. These grade 145 (i.e. fiber areal weight of 145 gm/m²) prepreg tapes had a typical resin content of 34 wt. %. In all, three thermoplastic films were evaluated in these prepreg materials. All films tested were 0.0125 mm (0.0005 in.) thick. The total resin content of the interleafed system (i.e. interleaf plus matrix resin) was 40% by weight.

An experimental procedure similar to the one used by Byers [Ref 8] was used to study material resistance to low velocity impact. This method, which is widely used in the aircraft industry, measures the residual compression strength of 36 ply, $[(\pm 45/0/90/0/90)_2 / \pm 45/0/90 / \pm 45]$ s, laminates. In this test procedure, the 10.2 cm by 15.2 cm (4.0 in by 6.0 in) specimens are lightly clamped onto a steel plate which simply supports the specimens. The steel support plate has a 7.6 cm by 12.7 cm (3. in by 5. in) cut-out and sits on a concrete floor. A drop-weight impact is used to deliver a blow of 6.70 kJ per

meter of specimen thickness (1500 in-lb/in). After they have been impacted, the test panels are loaded to failure in compression using a test fixture which provides simple support along the specimen edges. This prevents gross specimen buckling during loading. In this test the laminate's residual strength is used as an indication of its resistance to impact.

Hinged, straight-sided double cantilever beam specimens [Ref 9] were used to measure Mode I delamination resistance. The specimens used in this program were 38.1 mm. (1.5 in.) wide, 22.9 cm (9.0 in.) long, and 24 plies thick. In the procedures employed in this study, 0.025 mm (.001 in.) thick Teflon strips were cured into the laminates at their midplanes to control crack initiation. Hinged tabs were attached to the specimens and were used to mount the specimen in the test machine. They ensured that no bending moments were applied to the specimens and eliminated Mode II load components. A detailed description of the test procedure employed in these tests is contained in Reference 9.

End notched flexure specimens [Ref 10] were used to measure the material's Mode II delamination resistance. This type of specimen has found wide acceptance throughout the aerospace industry because it provides a direct determination of interlaminar Mode II fracture toughness. The specimens used in this study were 24 plies thick, 25.4 mm (1.0 in.) wide, and 15.2 cm (6.0 in.) long. A Teflon strip was again implanted in one end the laminate at the midplane to serve as a controlled crack initiator. Mode II forward shear is induced by subjecting the specimen to 3-point flexure loading. Detailed descriptions of the test procedure and data reduction schemes are contained in Reference 11.

RESULTS

Impact Resistance

The results of the residual compression strength after impact tests are summarized in Table I (results are also presented for CYCOM[®] 907, a rubber modified epoxy resin which is often used as a benchmark for toughness.). The data indicates that the addition of the thin thermoplastic interleaves had a pronounced effect on the laminates impact resistance. Significant increases in residual compression strength were realized in both graphite/epoxy and graphite/bismaleimide laminates via this technique. The increases in CYCOM 1808's compression strength after impact (CSAI) ranged from 50% to 80% depending on the type of interleaf used. For example, the residual compression strength of CYCOM 1827 laminates increased from 217.9 MPa (31.6 ksi) to 313.7 MPa (45.5 ksi) with the addition of the thermoplastic interleaf.

All of the values listed for interleaved epoxy systems were much greater than 276.4 MPa (40.1 ksi) the residual compression strength of AS4/907 laminates impacted at this level. In fact, although it is difficult to compare CSAI data developed at different laboratories due to subtle variables such as test fixture compliance and energy absorbed by the test frame bed, it should be noted that these results are comparable to values given for thermoplastic matrix composites such as AS4/PEEK impacted at this energy level [Ref 12].

TABLE I
EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

PREPREG	GIC	GIIC	RESIDUAL COMPRESSION STRENGTH
	KJ/M ² (in-lb/in ²)	KJ/M ² (in-lb/in ²)	MPa (ksi)
Epoxy Matrix			
AS4/1808			
Uninterleafed	.231 (1.32)	1.37 (7.84)	220 (32.0)
Film A	.290 (1.66)	3.29 (18.8)	410 (59.6)
Film C	.222 (1.27)	2.87 (16.4)	329 (47.7)
Film E	.366 (2.09)	3.68 (21.0)	326 (47.3)
IM6/1808			
Uninterleafed	.263 (1.50)	1.29 (7.36)	202 (29.3)
Film A	.329 (1.88)	3.37 (19.26)	368 (53.4)
C6000/1827			
Uninterleafed	.219 (1.25)	1.23 (7.0)	218 (31.6)
Film E	.322 (1.84)	2.52 (14.4)	315 (45.7)
AS4/907			
Uninterleafed	.400 (2.29)	2.05 (11.7)	276 (40.1)
Bismaleimide Matrix			
IM6/3100			
Uninterleafed	.343 (1.96)*	.73 (4.15)	143 (20.7)
Film E	.635 (3.63)*	2.42 (13.8)	216 (31.3)
IM6/3100-21			
Uninterleafed	.255 (1.46)*	.84 (4.8)	148 (21.5)
Film E	.380 (2.17)*	2.00 (11.4)	252 (36.6)

* Note: Fiber bridging observed in these laminates.

As the data in the table indicates, significant increases in the bismaleimide systems' impact resistance were also realized through interleaving. Although the absolute values of the interleaved bismaleimide laminates' CSAI were lower than the interleaved epoxies', the percent increases in CSAI were comparable. Thus, the inherently lower impact resistance of the bismaleimide resins is the main contributing factor to the lower CSAI value of interleaved bismaleimide laminates. Interleaving is, in a sense, more effective when combined with tougher matrix systems.

The reasons for the improvement in residual compression strength are apparent when the damage resulting from the impact is examined. Results of previously reported investigations [Ref 13,14] have indicated that the pattern of damage development is significantly altered through interleaving. Ultrasonic C-scan inspection of the impacted laminates indicates that the size of internal delaminations is greatly reduced in the interleaved laminates.

The role of the interleaf in reducing impact damage was revealed when the impacted specimens were sectioned and examined. Although transverse cracks develop within the individual plies as a result of the redistribution of impact-induced shear stresses, the toughened ply interfaces do not delaminate as they do in the uninterleaved laminates. This is illustrated in Figure 4 which shows photomicrographs of typical transverse cracks which developed in laminates made from interleaved and baseline AS4/1808 prepreg. Damage in the interleaved laminates is limited, for the most part, to a system of somewhat harmless transverse cracks. The delaminations that do develop under impact are fewer in number and much smaller than those found in uninterleaved laminates. They also tend to be located in the lower half of the specimen [Ref 13].

Delamination Resistance

Although the interleaves themselves demonstrate tough ductile behavior, the test results (Table 1) illustrate that only nominal increases in the material's Mode I strain energy release rate were realized in the interleaved laminates.

The mechanisms which lead to these results were apparent when the failure surfaces were examined. Photomicrographs of the fracture surfaces indicated that their overall surface topographies were similar to those of the uninterleaved laminates; they were smooth and devoid of prominent features. The crack fronts tended to propagate mainly through the thin layer of matrix resin at the prepreg-interleaf interface. The photomicrographs also indicated, however, that portions of the interleaf had been pulled away by the intersecting crack front, as shown in Fig 5. These interleaf pull-outs were found at many sites along the length of the interleaved specimens. Unfortunately, the interlayers do not display large scale deformation or tearing even in the pull-out region. This may be due to the constraining effect of the surrounding lamina and to the thinness of the interleaf films. It may also explain why interleaving only slightly increases GIC.

In contrast to the failure surfaces of the Mode I fracture specimens, the interleaf materials were highly deformed under Mode II crack growth. Fractographic features similar to those seen in uninterleaved specimens, i.e. hackles or lacerations, were found on the surfaces of the failed interleaved laminates. The features found in the interleaves were, however, an order of magnitude larger than those typically found in the matrix resins of uninterleaved specimens, as shown in Fig 6. The ductility of the interleaves is fully evident in these fractographs; the interleaf was peeled back and torn away as the two laminate surfaces slid over one another under the Mode II, forward shear loading.

Crack propagation through the tough interlayer in this manner should raise the overall GIC. The data in the table confirms this observation. The interleaved laminates' Mode II strain energy release rates were two to three times greater than their uninterleaved counterparts'. This was true of both graphite/epoxy and graphite/bismaleimide systems.

DISCUSSION

An important result of this investigation is the correlation between the two measures of toughness and the interleaved laminates' impact resistance. While several investigators [Ref 15,16] have linked impact resistance to interlaminar fracture toughness, these studies have considered only Mode I delamination growth. Figure 7 plots the residual compression strength after impact vs. the Mode I strain energy release rates for the interleaved and noninterleaved systems listed in Table 1. The general trend of increased damage tolerance with increased GIC as observed by other investigators holds for the uninterleaved, baseline systems. This correlation does not hold, however, when the interleaved laminates are considered. As noted earlier, the Mode I strain energy release rates of these systems are only slightly higher than the uninterleaved laminates'; their residual compression strengths after impact are, however, much greater than the baseline systems'. GIC does not appear to be a good general indicator of damage tolerance.

A good correlation of toughness and impact resistance is seen, however, when GIC is plotted vs. residual compression strength. Figure 8 plots these data for the interleaved and baseline systems discussed above. In this case, all the data falls along the same general line indicating that the Mode II strain energy release rate may be a better overall indicator of the material's impact resistance.

These results support the analytical work of Bostaph and Elber [Ref 17]. They developed a fracture mechanics analysis based on large deflection plate mechanics to describe the progress of delamination damage in a composite plate struck by a hard spherical object. Their analysis indicates that the extent of impact-induced delamination is a function of the critical shear strain energy release rate of the matrix.

Further evidence of the significance of interlaminar shear in impact-induced delamination is found when the delaminated surfaces are examined. Fractographic investigations of these surfaces [Ref 13, 18] indicate that they exhibit the hackle patterns commonly observed in Mode II (i.e. End Notched Flexure) shear specimens [Ref 19,10].

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this investigation of of thermoplastic interleaved composites led to the following conclusions:

1. Interleaving with thermoplastic films significantly increased the damage tolerance of graphite/epoxy and graphite/bismaleimide material systems. The residual compression strengths of these materials was increased by as much as 80% with the addition of these films.

2. Interleafing had only a minimal effect on the Mode I strain energy release rate of these systems. The interleaves exhibited very little deformation at those locations where the crack front intersected the film.
3. Interleafing greatly improved the material's Mode II strain energy release rate. The interleaved laminates' GIICs were two to three times greater than their uninterleafed counterparts'. The interleaves were highly deformed under this forward shear loading.
4. A good correlation of toughness, as measured by the GIIC, and impact resistance was also demonstrated.

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Figure 1. Interleafed Prepreg Construction.

Figure 2. Thermoset Interleafs Co-Cure with Prepreg Resin and Remain Discrete Layers.

Figure 3. Thermoplastic Interleaf-Lamina Bond is established during Laminate Cure.

Baseline Laminate

Interleaved Laminate

Figure 4. Impact-Induced Transverse Cracks Develop in Interleaved Laminates; Delamination is Suppressed.

Figure 5. Interleaf Films Display Little Deformation Under Mode I Loading.

Figure 6. Interleaf Films are Highly Deformed Under Mode II Loading.

Figure 7. A poor correlation of Mode I Strain Energy Release Rate and Impact Resistance was noted.

Figure 8. Mode II Strain Energy Release Rate is a Good Indicator of Impact Resistance.